

RACES, RACIAL COMPOSITION OF THE POPULATION.

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Annotation: In this article, the composition of races, their origin, the composition of races divided into species and species, the processes of reproduction of races in the body, the distribution by continents, is illuminated.

Key words: race, signs of race, main races, interval racial forms, europoid, mongoloid, negroid.

People from ancient times lived in a collective - collective blood brotherhood. The most popular of such units are their racial and ethnic units. The race is a historically formed territorial unit, the origin of which people, the structure and appearance of which are similar in govda. There are different opinions about the emergence of races and the origin of racial characters and characteristics between people, and the widespread are two:

"Polysentrism"

"Monocentrism"

Part of anthropologists believe that races began to be formed much earlier. This is the theory of "palisentrism". The factors of the second group are that now a person of the present time was formed in one center, then the emptiness began to spread to different parts of the world of people. This is the theory of "monocentrism". Races are divided according to the appearance of the Peoples mainly dish and the differences in it. In the Earth's sphere, three large races are distinguished: the europoid, the mongoloid, and the negroid, as well as many mixed race forms. Three races can not cover all the inhabitants of the world. In the territories close to these great races, peoples with signs of all different races lived

from ancient times. In later periods, mixed species between different races are also increasing as a result of increased race marriages. Mixed races between different races are divided into 2 groups: “ancient mixed forms, medieval and new era forms”.

Now we will briefly get acquainted with the geographical distribution of the forms of the main great races and mixed races.

The europoid race :

1. Northern europoid.
2. Medium-sized europoid.
3. Southern europoid.

Representatives of this race include 40% of the world's population. This large race is currently divided into 3 groups.

- 1) the height of the representatives of the northern group living in Northern Europe will be rod, sochi (curly) yellow, blue-eyed.
- 2) as for the Middle Europoid group: the hair of representatives of this race, different from the northern europoid, is smooth, the face-structure, the gavda structure is different in subsequent records.
- 3) the height of the representatives of the southern group living in southern Europe, North Africa, Old Asia, northern India comes from the branch, the skin is from the larynx, the hair is black, the chest is black. And the peoples of the Balkan Peninsula have a round head. Being black-haired, they also belong to this group. "Dinara is also referred to as” race”.

The Mongoloid race:

1. Asia Network
2. The American network includes 20% of the world's population. The Mongoloid race is also divided into two groups:.

There are different types within the Asian group. The American generation of the Mongoloid race includes the indigenous population of North and South America “Indians”. The main signs of the Mongoloid race: the color of the body bug'doyoyoy rang rang rang rang rang rang rang, the eyes are narrowed, the cheeks are protruding, the hair is straight. The Asian network of the Mongoloid race is also divided into the

northern and southern mongoloid race. The race of the Negroid: includes 15% of the world's population. The main race signs: the color of the skin is black, the hair is black and curly, the nose is wide, the lips are thick.

The Negroid race is also divided into two branches: the African and Okyanian networks. The African network of the equatorial race includes those peoples that live in yani, located in the south of the Sahara-the Negro. And to the network of Oceania melonesians. New Guinea caks, including the indigenous peoples of Australia. Mixed race forms: ancient mixed race forms or types include Efiop West Sudan type. Many of their signs are similar to Arabs. But they are black, like the Negroids. The ancient mixed forms between the Mongoloid and the Europoid live in the southern part of Western Siberia. The second large group of araslh racial forms includes mixed forms of the Middle Ages and the new era. One of the regions in which such aralsh forms are distributed is the Central Asian republics. Mixed forms, in turn, are divided into two types.

In the Middle oasis of the races of the middle and New Era, 2 types are distinguished: the first type: the Turon type or the Southern type-to this type are mainly the Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, with more signs of the mongoloid race. The second type: Central Asian type: these include Uzbeks, Turkmen, which are preserved signs characteristic of the southern generation of the europoid race.

Among the three major major races in the world in general, many other mixed forms and types have come into being and come into being.

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